

The Strength, Ductility and Failure of Thermoplastics Reinforced with Short-Glass Fibres

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ABSTRACT

Injection moulded test pieces have been prepared from nylon 6 reinforced with E-glass fibres finished with two different size formulations, both with and without silane coupling agents. Mechanical tests indicate that stiffness, strength, ductility and toughness are all enhanced by the use of the coupling agent, especially if the material has been exposed to an aqueous environment. A ductile/brittle failure mode has been observed which accounts for the rather low ductility associated with this class of material.

INTRODUCTION

Improvements in mechanical properties may be achieved by the incorporation of short glass-fibres into thermoplastics. The properties are dependent on a complex interaction of several variables; principally the fibre concentration, fibre length and orientation distribution and the strength of the interfacial bond. Optimum strength and stiffness results from long, aligned fibres which are well bonded to the matrix but this usually also results in a low ductility. The actual length and orientation distributions obtained will, however, be dictated by the processing route used, the fibre length is often reduced to less than the optimum and flow-induced orientation gives considerable anisotropy. The interfacial bond strength may be controlled by the application of coupling agents which are designed not only to improve the bond, but also to enhance strength retention under adverse environmental conditions. The sizing system employed may also be used to exert some control over the fibre-length distribution by modification of the glass-strand integrity, which affects the ease with which the strands disperse during processing.

Previous work on glass and carbon filled nylon 66 (1,2) has shown that increases in fibre fraction (V_f), fibre length and interfacial bond strength result in improved stiffness, higher strength but reduced ductility. In this investigation similar property trends have been observed. The effect of the interface is, however, very complex; it has been assessed by using fibres treated with two silanes and two film forming compounds. Samples were tested after a short environmental conditioning period and also after boiling water treatment which highlighted the ability of the silane to retain bond integrity (3).

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used were a single grade of polyamide 6 (Maranyl F114) supplied by ICI Ltd and a range of E-glass rovings. Those fibres designated 'A' had a polyurethane based size which in types III and IV incorporated a proprietary silane coupling agent. Fibres designated 'B', from a different manufacturer, were coated with a cationic polyelectrolyte epoxy-derivative film former, a silane coupling agent was added in types II and III only. A co-extrusion compounding technique was used to prepare moulding granules from the polymer and fibre; it was a modified version of that employed by Bader and Bowyer (4) whereby the polymer is coated onto a continuous roving of glass fibre, the resulting coaxial fibre/polymer extrudate then being chopped into pellets. It should be noted that the fibres are not fully wetted and impregnated during this compounding operation, being merely encased in a sheath of polymer. The fibres themselves are bound together by the film former in the size which preserves strand integrity. The pellets were charged directly into a screw pre-plasticizing injection moulding machine and moulded into tensile test bars. The degree of fibre dispersion and extent of fibre breakage were controlled by the machine settings: The most important parameter being the screw back-pressure. In this work a pellet length of 4mm was found to give the best length distribution and dispersion. The injection moulded tensile test bars were 150mm long and had a gauge portion 60 x 12 x 3mm. The Charpy-type impact test pieces were machined from the gauge portions of tensile bars and were 40mm long with a 2mm saw-cut notch in one edge; the notch was further sharpened by cutting with a scalpel blade immediately prior to testing. After moulding, the test bars were conditioned at 20°C and 50% relative humidity for 28-30 days to allow some degree of moisture content stabilization. Some test pieces were further treated by boiling in distilled water for 48hrs, they were then cooled to room temperature, superficially dried and tested immediately. Tensile testing was conducted on an Instron model 1195 testing machine; load, strain and acoustic emission were recorded autographically. A Charpy type machine was used for impact testing with an impact velocity of 3ms⁻¹ and a kinetic energy of 5J. The fibre fraction, fibre length and diameter distributions were determined for each batch of material.

In conjunction with the mechanical testing, an extensive programme of optical and scanning electron microscopy was conducted in order to follow the sequence of microstructural damage leading up to final failure.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Two series of mouldings were made with a nominal 0.1V_f and 0.25V_f of glass-fibre respectively. Their mechanical properties are summarised in Table I. It should be noted that the V_f for the BI material was 0.17 due to an experimental anomaly. Fibre diameters ranged from 10-16 µm but this appears to have had little influence on the average aspect-ratios measured on the moulded material. Again that of the BI batch is slightly anomalous being 31, corresponding to an average fibre length of 320 µm, whilst the remainder lie close to a ratio of 25, corresponding to average lengths of 250-270 µm, for the 10 µm diameter fibre, to 370 µm in the 16 µm diameter material. The aspect ratios have been calculated on the measured average diameter rather than the nominal values quoted in Table I. In all cases there was a wide spread of fibre lengths in the moulding with a significant proportion of the fibres being much longer than the average. For example in batch A IV the number-average fibre length was 370 µm but 20% of the fibres exceeded 500µm and there were many of over 1mm. This accounts for the fact that the mechanical properties of the "dry" materials are rather better than would be calculated for a fibre the average length quoted.

TABLE I
PROPERTIES OF INJECTION MOULDED GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED NYLON 6 COMPOUNDS

Material	Fibre Diameter d (μm)	Average aspect ratio \bar{R}	Volume fraction V_f	Test condition	Tensile Modulus E (GPa)	Failure Stress σ_u (MPa)	Failure Strain ϵ_u (%)	Impact Energy Y_C (kJ/m^2)	Remarks
A I	12	25	0.1	Dry	4.79	82.6	2.4	12.9	PU size
				Wet	1.22	31.7	>25		
A II	16	25	0.25	Dry	10.7	102	1.3	16.8	no silane
				Wet	2.16	28.8	15		
A III	12	26	0.1	Dry	4.64	79.3	2.5	13.0	
				Wet	1.09	31.7	>25		
A IV	16	25	0.25	Dry	10.0	106	1.4	14.9	
				Wet	2.12	28.7	15		
A III	12	26	0.1	Dry	5.10	101	3.0	14.6	PU size
				Wet	2.67	50.8	5.3		
A IV	16	25	0.25	Dry	11.1	169	2.2	19.7	with silane
				Wet	4.84	84.0	3.3		
B I	10	31	0.1	Dry	5.40	113	3.0	16.5	
				Wet	2.77	55.8	3.7		
B II	10	25	0.25	Dry	10.2	164	2.9	26.4	
				Wet	5.34	95.0	4.3		
B I	10	31	0.17	Dry	7.19	128	2.7	25.4	Polyelectrolyte size - no silane
				Wet	5.20	31.2	16		
B II	10	25	0.25	Dry	10.8	159	2.2	26.4	Polyelectrolyte size - with silane
				Wet	4.2	29.1	5.9		
B III	13	22	0.1	Dry	4.8	95.4	2.4	16.8	
				Wet	2.38	31.9	9		
B III	13	22	0.25	Dry	11.4	157	2.0	27.9	
				Wet	4.75	62.9	1.9		
B III	13	22	0.1	Dry	4.50	100	3.0	16.8	
				Wet	2.40	32.7	17		
B III	13	22	0.25	Dry	9.78	152	1.7	25.6	
				Wet	4.60	60.4	2.1		

It will be seen that in all cases increasing the V_f from 0.1 to 0.25 results in a corresponding increase to the "dry" stiffness and strength but a decrease in the ductility. In the batch A material the omission of the silane coupling agent from the size results in marginally lower stiffness, significantly lower strength and, perhaps surprisingly, a reduction in ductility. On the other hand the effect of the silane is much less apparent on the "dry" properties of the B material. However, when the "wet" results are compared it is seen that the batches without the silane couplant suffer a much more drastic reduction in stiffness and strength. There is also a significant reduction in the properties of the coupled materials and it is noteworthy that the reductions in stiffness and strength are not compensated by corresponding increases in ductility. It was possible to conduct impact tests only on the "dry" material but here it is quite clear that the lower stiffness and strength of the uncoupled materials does not enhance the toughness. In fact the toughness of the uncoupled materials of batch A is significantly lower than that of the coupled versions, whilst in batch B there is little difference.

In figure 1 a set of typical stress/strain curves are shown which emphasise the above points. Note that the toughest materials are, in fact, the strongest! A pair of stress/strain curves are compared in more detail in figure 2. Note the lower stiffness, strength and ductility of the uncoupled material. It was also observed that the total acoustic emission was much lower in the uncoupled materials. The implication being that when the interface bond is weak it debonds at lower stress with consequent much lower levels of energy to contribute to the acoustic emission count recorded.

The mechanical test results may be summarised by stating that the silane coupling agents appear to work most effectively. In most cases stiffness, strength and ductility and toughness were all enhanced to a limited extent in the "dry" condition. In the "wet" condition the silane was essential, otherwise the glass-fibre reinforcement was virtually ineffective.

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 1 shows typical stress/strain curves for the 7 materials tested in both the dry and wet state. In Fig 2 the effects of silane coupling are shown. The uncoupled material, A I, has a much lower strength and ductility, also much less acoustic emission was recorded.

FAILURE BEHAVIOUR

A number of micro-failure processes have been identified in fibre reinforced thermoplastics. These include fibre fracture, matrix cracking, debonding at the fibre/matrix interface and flow of the matrix. The operative process depends on the interface bond strength and the fibre distribution. In discontinuous fibre composites the strain concentrations in the matrix associated with the fibre ends always lead to local debonding and/or cracking, or localised plastic flow of the matrix.

When testing the samples it was observed that as the load increased, strain bands, visible as narrow milky white regions, formed across the specimen at an angle to the tensile axis. The onset of this phenomenon was gradual and its severity increased with strain until final fracture occurred in a sudden and brittle manner at one of the more severe bands (Fig. 3). The fracture however followed the band only part way across the section. The formation of the bands is attributed to localised fibre debonding and associated matrix flow, the damage regions being initiated by strain concentrations at fibre ends or crossover points.

Microscopic examination of sections cut from the test bars revealed that the fibre alignment distribution was analogous to a laminated structure (5), comprising a thin skin of random in plane orientation, thicker intermediate layers where the fibres were strongly aligned in the flow direction, and a central or core region where the fibres had a pronounced transverse bias. This multilayer structure was apparent in all samples examined, however it was noted that the alignment was more developed when fibre length and volume fraction were higher.

In the broken samples examined, matrix cracking was not extensive and, if observed at all, was confined to regions adjacent to the final fracture path.

Fig 3: Portions of the gauge length of two tensile test pieces both showing extensive strain banding. In the right hand photograph the fracture path can be seen to run partly through a strain band.

Fig 4

Fig 5

Fig 4: A reflected light photomicrograph showing extensive matrix cracking adjacent to the main fracture (top) in a tensile test bar.

Fig 5: A portion of the same field as, Fig 4, at a higher magnification and by transmitted light. Evidence of fibre debonding and pull-out can be seen either side of the crack.

The example shown in Fig. 4, whilst being atypical, does serve to illustrate some useful points. The extensive cracking is considered to be a direct result of the final fracture process, since no progressive crack growth had been observed during testing; the rapid propagation of the final brittle crack has been impeded and diverted by the presence of the fibres. Fig. (5) is from the same area viewed under transmitted light and, clearly visible, either side of the crack are debonded fibres and sockets left by fibres in the process of pulling out of the matrix. In none of the materials examined was extensive fibre fracture, prior to final failure, observed either during microscopic observation of sections, or from fibre length distribution analysis of strained material. We conclude that fibre fracture does not significantly contribute to the general damage development, prior to the final catastrophic failure sequence.

Microscopic examination of the strain banding showed that the bands consisted of regions of intense debonding, the surrounding areas having suffered comparatively little damage apart from debonded fibre ends. There was an absence of matrix cracking within the bands, despite the extensive debonding and the bands were confined to the central, misaligned core region of the samples. To examine closely the order of events leading to failure a number of specially prepared samples were strained in-situ under the microscope.

Significantly different behaviour was observed between the coupled and uncoupled materials. The coupled samples showed no debonding prior to straining, and when extended, the order of events was as follows: Firstly, many fibre ends debonded, each of these events was virtually instantaneous, subsequently debonding occurred at fibre crossover points and also progressed along fibres from their debonded ends. Their reinforcing capability was thus reduced and the local strains redistributed causing further debonding in adjacent regions. This resulted in a localisation of the damage into 'bands' of debonded fibres. Final failure occurred through one of the most severe bands with the debonded fibres being pulled out at the fracture surface.

The uncoupled samples showed debonding prior to testing especially in the core regions, this is attributed to the residual thermal stress resulting from the different thermal contraction of the axially and normally aligned layers through the section. Indications of a weaker bond were also obtained during the specimen polishing stage where it was noted that the uncoupled fibres were displaced or ripped out of the matrix much more easily than in the coupled materials. During straining sudden end-debonding events were not generally observed (because they had already debonded during moulding), the debonding observed was principally along transversely orientated fibres.

Fig 6: Highly developed strain bands showing crack initiation on the surface of a tensile test piece strained in the wet condition.

It was more extensive than in the coupled materials and was not so localised (i.e. the bands were not as pronounced). In the case of the "wet" materials the debonding was even more extensive and in some cases, particularly in the uncoupled materials at low V_f , strain bands were observed to run right across the section (Fig. 6), they were not just confined to the misaligned core region as in the "dry" materials.

The fracture surfaces were examined in the scanning electron microscope. Over most fracture surfaces the nylon matrix had failed in a predominantly brittle manner with extensive fibre pullout. Despite this general brittle appearance however, the majority of samples had regions showing ductile matrix flow. These regions were always in the misaligned core regions of the samples and was more pronounced in lower V_f materials, which have higher failure strains.

Fig 7

Fig 7: A ductile area on a typical tensile fracture surface. The pulled out fibres are misaligned and very "clean". The matrix shows much evidence of ductile flow.

Fig 8

Fig 8: A brittle region of the same fracture. The pulled out fibres have matrix debris still attached.

Figs. 7 and 8 show these ductile and brittle matrix regions observed in the same specimen. In the ductile region the fibres are clearly less well aligned and have pulled out much more cleanly than those in the brittle region which have a lot of matrix adhering to them. The condition of the pulled out fibre surfaces is generally considered indicative of the strength of the fibre matrix interfacial bond, clean fibres indicating poor bonding and 'dirty' fibres indicating a strong bond. The appearance of the ductile regions is considered to be a result of the relatively slow speed debonding and strain banding process described above, whilst in the brittle area, failure was by fast crack propagation. Despite the obvious difference in bond strength indicated by the mechanical properties and optical examination of the coupled and uncoupled materials, their fracture surfaces were not significantly or consistently different. Clean fibre, ductile matrix regions were observed with all sizing systems as were brittle areas containing fibres with adhering matrix.

Close examination of characteristic striations on the brittle matrix fracture surface often indicated fracture initiation points which were usually identified as broken fibres or fibre ends. An example is shown in Fig. 9. The circular crack front which originated at a fibre end has radiated outwards where it intersects the main fracture path.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The mechanical test results have shown the critical importance of a properly formulated coupling agent to ensure optimum stiffness, strength and ductility especially when the material is exposed to water. The strain to failure of the more highly reinforced materials is very low, generally below that of the reinforcing fibre. There appears to be no possibility of increasing either ductility or toughness by decreasing the interface strength. The resulting loss of stiffness and strength appears to be the more dominant factor.

A general picture of the failure sequence is emerging from this work. Initial debonding is localised in the misaligned core region, where there is a tensile residual stress, due to differential shrinkage and surface chilling effects associated with the injection moulding process. The damage is localised by the process of strain redistribution and this leads to the formation of strain bands, where highly localised ductile matrix flow is associated with the regions of intense debonding of the fibres from the matrix. As the strain bands

Fig 9: A typical "sporadic" crack initiation region in a brittle fracture area. The crack has initiated either at a fibre end or possibly when a fibre fractured. The circular arrest front is clearly visible.

develop, a higher proportion of the load must be carried by the stiffer and stronger aligned fibre layers. Final failure is initiated by a process of brittle crack propagation through these aligned regions. The critical factor in determining the rather low failure strain of the composite appears to be the low macroscopic strain associated with the formation of the strain bands in the weaker core material.

This hypothesis is consistent with several other observations. Thus if the bond strength is decreased, by omitting the silane, the core region debonds and forms strain bands more readily. The low acoustic emission recorded for uncoupled materials is consistent with the view that the core material was effectively debonded by the thermal stresses and thus debonding as such did not contribute to the acoustic output recorded.

It is conceivable that the failure strain and toughness could be enhanced by a suitable annealing treatment which would relieve the internal stress (in the absence of any associated embrittlement due for instance to enhanced crystallinity). Otherwise it would appear that the routes to enhanced performance must involve better fibre alignment (but greater anisotropy), stronger fibre/matrix bonding via better coupling agents and/or modification to the processing to ensure that the fibre aspect ratio is increased.

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